

Critical Making

D4.1 REVIEW OF MEASURES TO INTEGRATE YOUNG PEOPLE INTO THE MAKER COMMUNITY

About this document

Date	August 2021
Dissemination level	Public
Responsible Partner	TU Berlin
Work package	WP 4 - Case action: YOUNG TALENTS
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006285.

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Contributor	Comments
v1	26/04/21	Melanie Stilz	First outline of the deliverable
v2	09/07/21	Melanie Stilz, Samer Shawar, Regina Sipos	Adding content to main parts and discussion on focus of the deliverable and connection to critical making
v3	15/08/21	Melanie Stilz, Teresa Schäfer	Review comments; editing review suggestions and comments
v4	23/08/21	Melanie Stilz	Finalizing missing sections and conclusions

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V., Germany
H2020	Horizon2020 – The European Research Framework Programme
OER	Open Educational Resources
OSHW	Open Source Hardware
OSH	Open Science Hardware
R&I	Research & Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
STEM	Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics
STEAM	Science Technology Engineering Arts and Mathematics
TUB	Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
VTT	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY, Finland
WIF	Wikifactory Europe SL, Spain
WP	Work Package
WP1	Project Management
WP2	Building the critical making knowledge-base: concept & methods
WP3	Case Action: GENDER
WP4	Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS
WP5	Case Action: OPENNESS
WP6	Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications
WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Despite the growing number of activities in the education sector labelled as “Making”, there is no real consensus on what constitutes educational Making, what counts as Making and where it differs from the rising number of STEM promotion activities in recent years. We suggest it’s not only the creative element - see also the discussion around STEAM education - but also the critical perspective and attitude that the Maker¹ Movement brings into Maker Education. The review of measures to integrate young people in Germany into the Maker Community shows that at least in the German context there is no consistent definition of **Maker Education** and it is often seen as a “more engaging way to teach technology” with an entrepreneurial spirit at best but little attention to the critical and democratizing elements.

¹ In this report we use the term “Maker” as in “Makerspace” and “Maker Education” despite its male connotation in German. This might be changed in later publications, but as it is the dominant wording in the literature it was tentatively adopted here.

INTRODUCTION

Making Activities, Maker Education or educational approaches with or connected to Makerspaces and Fab Labs have gained visibility and popularity in recent years (Stilz et al., 2020). One dominant reason for including Maker approaches in educational settings has been the shortage of science, technology, engineering and math (“STEM”) graduates and the search for new ways to attract more young people - and girls in particular - for those subjects (Pinto, 2016). But with increasing visibility, there is also growing attention to other potentials of Making in education: entrepreneurial education (Dali, 2015; Schön et al., 2018), education for sustainable development („Digital Literacy Lab“, o. J.: MacDowell, 2021) or creativity and innovation (Resnick & Rosenbaum, 2016;). Making Activities have often been put in the context of critical pedagogy and authors like Paolo Freire (Torres & Noguera, 2008; Tuhkala et al., 2019). Yet there is little academic writing on critical making in education.

In this review we want to gain a first understanding, how and where Making Activities for children and youth are taking place, which formats prevail and what educational goals they pursue. It is based on the results of our first Critical Making Workshop held in March 2021, where we invited experts - including those who are part of this consortium - in the field of Making Education and gathered examples of spaces, actors and programs for children and youth. Subsequently, two interviews were conducted with well connected Maker Education practitioners to enrich our analyses with their know-how and experiences. Due to the extensive number of activities linked to Making in education globally we chose to use Germany as a case example. In a second step we want to explore if and how these initiatives are linked to the broader Maker Community and whether the educational programmes can be seen “critical” in the sense of critical making and RRI.

I. EDUCATION PROVIDERS

Though “making” was originally linked to physical workshops, making activities are now offered in various forms and mingle with other types of extracurricular activities like science education. The first Making Education activities in Germany that used the name “making” were those offered by Fab Labs and Makerspaces in the late 2000’s. Nonetheless, crafting, tinkering and hacking in workshops, repair cafés or hackerspaces had their ties to education and civil society long before (Baier, 2016).

PRIVATE SECTOR

With the hard- and software involved, Making Activities are also attractive to the private sector. The Making Activities offered by those actors are often free of charge or subsidized, but are linked with commercial products that are used, like educational robots or 3D modelling software. Compared to the general “digital education” field, however, the examples for commercial Maker Education offers are few. Reasons might be the strong links between Maker Culture, democratization of technological practices (Tanenbaum et al., 2013) and the Open Source Movement (Dougherty, 2012) that conflict with purely monetary interests. More common in the private sector are thus the funding of Making Activities as acts of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) with no (tangible) financial gain attached or carried out by corporate foundations. Prominent example is the Calliope Mini microcontroller for schools, an Open Hard- and Software product funded among others by Deutsche Telekom Stiftung, Google, Cornelsen, Bosch and SAP (Förschler, 2018) and that is linked with countless sponsorship projects by its donors (Leithold, 2017).

ASSOCIATIONS

Open Workshops

Most Fab Labs², Makerspaces and other Open Workshops³, that are not primarily youth or education focussed, also offer courses or mentorship for children and youth. With both the professional equipment and an active community that is used to sharing knowledge and helping each other, these places are central to Maker Education. As in other tech related educational settings, attracting not only “white, male, privileged” youth, but a more diverse group can be challenging. Thus, a lot of these spaces make the effort of collaborating with educational institutions or programs. They can also play a vital role in supporting teachers that feel insecure or have reservations towards digital technology. With few existing formal ties between Open Workshops and schools, however, these partnerships have proven not to be easy to establish and maintain.

Non-profit actors

More common in the Maker Education are non-profit associations and progressive education stakeholders that either include making activities into their offerings or have a history in innovative or critical educational approaches. They often have their own premises they use for courses, but also collaborate with Open Workshops, schools, youth centres or other public institutions where courses can take place.

PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS

The German Network “Schülerlabore” (pupils’ laboratories) was originally formed to make science, in particular natural science and engineering education, more tangible for children and youth (Stilz & Mennike, 2021).

² for the list of all Fab Labs see <https://www.fablabs.io/labs>

³ for a list of Open Workshops in German see <https://www.offene-werkstaetten.org/werkstatt-suche>

Makerspaces are seen as a recent variant of these labs (Schön et al., 2019). The laboratories are usually affiliated with public institutions like universities or museums; therefore, they are predominantly based in bigger cities (see fig. 1), but there is also a growing number of mobile offerings. The network list 423 laboratories on their website and offer a searchable map of all registered spaces⁴. The majority still addresses STEM subjects, but a growing number offers humanities or interdisciplinary approaches.

Figure 1: pupils' laboratories in Germany

Another new actor in the landscape of Maker Education are public libraries. With the growing detachment of books and magazines from physical spaces, libraries search for new ways to meet their educational mandate and attract (new) visitors. Following international examples, filling the now often empty

⁴ for more information see <https://www.schuelerlabor-atlas.de/home/>

reading rooms with a Makerspace and new purpose gains popularity (BuB, 2016).

SCHOOL MAKERSPACES

Makerspaces in schools are still the exception, but their numbers grow. In search of “21st century education” and innovative digital formats and approaches, newly established schools often see a digital workshop or Makerspace as a promising addition. The second group of school Makerspaces result from existing workshop infrastructures at technical or vocational schools and schools that offer vocational orientation (*Forum Arbeitslehre*, 2016). These mostly wood, metal or textile / sewing workshops or training kitchens that have often been used for crafting and home economics, lost their prevocational function with declining numbers in traditional craftsmanship and housekeeping as a full-time occupation. Like libraries, some of these schools manage to reinvent these traditional workshops. They complement them with new tools and purposes like affordable and easy to use 3D modelling and printing, simple electronics or multimedia content development. Fewer even completely refurbish and rebrand them as Fab Labs or Makerspaces and gain recognition again. There are also occasional funding opportunities that schools can apply for, for equipping such spaces⁵. Nonetheless, Makerspaces in schools almost exclusively depend on the commitment of individual teachers to invest personal time and resources, whether they are newly built or repurposed. Thereby, many of the existing school workshops also lie idle when schools neither have the capacity nor the funding to renew them, find new purposes for integrating them in contemporary vocational orientation and keep them running.

⁵ see for example <https://www.telekom-stiftung.de/aktivitaeten/gestaltbar-die-digitale-werkstatt>

ONLINE OFFERS

With the growing interest in Making Education in Germany and more recently with the pandemic and closed schools, digital offerings like teaching material, but also webinars, self-learning courses and MOOCS gained visibility and popularity. Most of these offers have been publicly funded in some way, e.g. are the result of research projects and are thus free of charge OER. Others can be purchased, often combined with a construction kit that contains the necessary hardware and materials.

Mixed

Unsurprisingly, formats can also vary and mix. Not only between online and offline formats, also working in traditional classrooms can be combined with visits in Open Workshops or public library Makerspaces and self-learning. Digital tools with interaction and collaboration features can help organize these combinations of different offline and online spaces, similarly field research with interviews and field visits can be integrated into online courses. Nonetheless, these hybrid forms are still the exception when working with children and youth. They afford equipment, infrastructure and flexibility that most schools cannot offer (Ingold et al., 2019).

OTHER

As the interest in Making Activities is growing and not all schools are close enough to Open Workshops, there are also a number of Mobile Makerspace projects. They mostly visit schools, but also other public institutions like libraries or events like fairs and festivals. These events can also be seen as a “provider” itself, though they usually just bring all of the above-mentioned actors together in one place: from the large-scale Maker Faire to small local educational events with a few booths and workshops.

Table 1: Education Providers

Providers	Examples
Private Sector and associations	Haba Digital https://digitalwerkstatt.de/ Technologiestiftung Berlin https://www.technologiestiftung-berlin.de/
Open Labs and Workshops	Verstehbahnhof Fürstenberg https://www.verstehbahnhof.de/
Public Institutions	Futurium Lab https://futurium.de/de/futurium-lab
School Makerspaces	School Makerspace Gustav-Falke-Schule https://makerspace.medialepfade.org/
Online platforms	Tüftelakademie https://tueftelakademie.de/
Festivals and competitions	Maker Faire https://maker-faire.de/
Other	Mobile Lab https://erfindergarden.de/mobile-fab-lab/

II. TARGET GROUP AND GOALS

Despite the multiplier role of teachers for reaching a young audience, educational Making Activities are predominantly targeted at children and youth and to a lesser extent at teachers or other pedagogical staff. The reasons for this are various. The interdisciplinary character of Making, the specific requirements regarding methodology, time and equipment as well as the lack of a clear economical gain - unlike for example Computer Science, Making does not directly train for desperately needed professional skills - make it hard to build a strong lobby among educators and others.

PUPILS

Educational Making Activities originally mostly targeted youth, starting from an age of about 12 years. Yet programs for a younger audience are increasing, as there are strong arguments to involve younger pupils. Making Activities offer a playful way to make first experiences with electronics and digital tools. This also bears the chance of bringing girls in touch with technology before they are influenced by gender stereotypes regarding their capabilities and interests (Wittemyer et al., 2014). With its creative and hands-on approach to technology and digital topics it is also often described as more suitable for children that have difficulties understanding abstract mathematical concepts linked with programming and computer science in general. Making Activities can also help foster learning motivation and a sense of self-efficacy by producing concrete tangible results that are directly linked to the lives of young people (Katterfeldt et al., 2015).

STEM

As mentioned above, a large share of extracurricular activities that are or could be covered in a broader sense as “Making Activities” intend to attract more young people to STEM subjects, or rather MINT - Math, Informatics, Natural Sciences and Technology - as they are called in Germany. These

activities usually come with a particular focus on Computer Science related elements like robotics, physical computing, or programming. In these examples, “Making” is usually a means to an end: developing important digital skills among youth. Though this is not in itself objectionable, it certainly misses important characteristics of Maker Education and Critical Making and reduces Making to a mere instrument.

STEAM

In an attempt to a more open and creative view on STEM education, arts-based science, technology, engineering, and mathematics education (STEAM) - the German translation MINKT is less common - became a popular educational framework in recent years. The H2020 research project SySTEM collected organisations and STEAM activities across Europe and created a map that allows applying certain filters. It lists only 53 organizations in Germany⁶. Also, the other examples collected for this report demonstrate that “creativity” is a common buzzword in educational programs, but similar to “Making” the arts are mostly reduced to a didactical instrument to make learning STEM subjects and topics more attractive.

TEACHERS

Despite the growing interest in “digital education” and “21st century skills” there are few explicit “Maker Education” offers in teacher education and training. Mainly Computer Science, Physics and Engineering education work with typical “Maker Education Technologies” like microcontrollers or robots, but in most cases in the above-mentioned STEM education tradition. Some teacher training providers have recently included digital fabrication and electronic introductory courses for beginners as well as methodological approaches like Design Thinking. But the mostly traditional school settings and a tight syllabus make it difficult for teachers to adapt Making Activities in their teaching. Schools usually cannot offer the space, equipment and

⁶ for more information see <https://system2020.education/the-map/>

flexibility that is needed for Making activities, thus teachers are less motivated to invest time in the topic.

OPEN TO ANYONE

Open Workshops and Fab Labs usually offer their spaces and services to all interested persons. Some offer courses explicitly for children and youth, but also make efforts creating an atmosphere that makes them feel welcome at any time.

Table 2: Target group and goals

Target group and goals	Examples
Pupils	Pupils laboratories https://www.lernortlabor.de/
Teachers	Junge Tüftler https://junge-tueftler.de/angebot/schule
Open Workshops with offers for all age groups	Hobbyhimmel https://hobbyhimmel.de/
STEM subjects learning focus	Make-up your MINT https://www.make-up-your-mint.de/
STEAM subjects learning focus	Der Deutsche Multimediapreis mb21 https://www.mb21.de/ Make in Class https://www.makeinclass.eu/

Other topics like humanities or Education for Sustainable Development	Kieler Forschungswerkstatt https://www.forschungs-werkstatt.de/
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III. DURATION AND FUNDING

Making Activities for children and youth come at all sizes: from pop-up workshops at conferences lasting a few minutes to summer camps lasting several weeks.

SHORT-TERM

The shortest Making Activities are probably those at conferences and fairs with a lesser educational mission, but rather the goal to spark an interest in the topic. The above-mentioned Schülerlabore offer short-term courses of a few hours that teachers can book for their classes (Euler & Weißnigk, 2011). The labs themselves usually operate all year long with regular course offerings, some however only offer irregular events or holiday courses. The course concepts, due to the limited time and often clearly defined educational goal, usually follows a tight set of instructions, and leaves little time for exploration and experimentation.

Research projects and university offers

There has been a number of research projects in Maker Education in recent years with German involvement,

The Federal Ministry of Education and Research also announced their interest in the Maker Culture, with a particular focus on innovation, citizen participation and the goal to connect the Maker Culture with research and industry⁷. They also explicitly mention Maker Activities in their funding line

⁷ see also <https://www.bmbf.de/de/maker-szene-2128.html>

for STEM education (BMBF, 2020) and have in the past years funded a number of projects with a strong focus on Making.

CURRICULAR INTEGRATION

Despite the growing popularity of Making Activities and their use in Digital or STEM education, there are few public schools that include Making in their curriculum. Exceptions are private schools or public schools that are newly founded and that take a new path altogether: here we find a strong focus on interdisciplinarity, project-oriented learning and self-learning competence combined with digital technologies.

Other examples are schools that include Making activities into existing subjects, offer Making activities as elective subject or are currently testing how to include making in their curriculum. While Maker Education addresses desperately needed reforms and skills: technology and digital literacy, creativity, competence-based learning (Blikstein & Krannich, 2013; Martin, 2015) - it also conflicts with many entrenched German school traditions as mentioned above: tight curricular requirements in each of the strictly divided subject areas, cut into 45 minutes slots. Integrating Making Activities and opening a space for a change in learning culture is thus the more common path for German schools.

OPEN

Other than educational courses or training, educational Makerspaces or Open Workshops allow children to work on open-end projects and receive support and mentorship where needed. These spaces are still an exception in the German Maker Education landscape, but their popularity and numbers are rising.

COSTS AND FUNDING

Looking at STEAM activities in Germany, the SysTEM interactive map shows that most activities combine different sources of income, but public funding,

donations and various grants make by far the biggest share (SySTEM2020, 2021). This coincides with responses from other Making Activity providers.

Table 3: Duration and costs

Duration and funding	Example
Short Term Courses	https://jugendhackt.org/labs/
Research projects	„DOIT – Entrepreneurial skills for young social innovators in an open digital world“ https://www.doit-europe.net/
Curricular integration: schools with a focus on interdisciplinarity, project-oriented learning and self-learning competence. Taking a new path altogether (1) or integrating “Making” into existing course routines and structures (2).	1. Public comprehensive school KGS Niederrad http://kgs-niederrad.de/index.php/das-konzept/ 2. Public Carlo-Schmid secondary school https://www.carlo-schmid-oberschule.de/
Open offers	Open Workshop https://www.fablabkids.de/kurse/offene-werkstatt-fuer-jugendliche/
Public funding of institutions that offer programs for children and youth	TUMO Berlin https://berlin.tumo.de/
Grants from Foundations or the private sector funding offers that schools can	1. Make Your School – Eure Ideenwerkstatt

apply for (1) or funding programs that develop free courses and materials (2).	https://www.makeyourschool.de/ 2. Code your Life https://www.code-your-life.org/
Fees and co-funding	Mini Maker https://mini-maker.de/

IV. BEST AND WORST PRACTICES

Apart from the examples for measures to integrate young people into the maker community, the participants of the Critical Making workshop were also asked to contribute recommendations as best and worst practices. Encouragingly, the positive examples clearly prevailed.

BEST PRACTICES

About half of the best practices concerned recommendations regarding the methodology / pedagogical approaches of Making Activities, which can also be seen as the path to building the “Maker Mindset”. The other half addressed conceptual and strategic aspects, how Making activities should be approached but also communicated.

Methodological aspects / building a Maker Mindset

- start with user research
- Ask questions - build understanding
- start with a problem to be solved
- "senseless" playing around
- low threshold, high ceiling
- inspiration showers

- prototyping as the process of ideation
- "idea shopping (or other term for shopping - suggestions?)"
- Stimulate invention, gambiarras, how to work yourself around with what you have. In portuguese: "sevirismo""cambiarra" "jeitinhi"
- Develop a set of guidelines that provide a framework for openly documenting everything about the making of the project.
- Promote freedom of expression and power of creativity and collective communion
- Mistakes are OK and its great to make some to learn! Establishing a "Fehlerkultur"
- working on eyelevel
- group assessment / define rules for the making community --> implement a mindset
- failing is allowed, encouraged, seen as an opportunity to learn
- Freedom to make
- innovative materials (conductive ink, fabrics, edible filament, etc.)
- using & combining everything!
- limit materials
- Use time banks and cooperative values
- Fun and Joy!

Strategic / conceptual aspects

- "use and think the STEAM term"
- make the "A"(rts) great!
- search for gender sensitive wording - e.g. "Monster" instead of robot
- Make things that make sense
- Fight inequality on a intersectional approach
- Aim to give back more than you take from the environment
- Design for the present and future
- build social capacity
- Promote diversity not only of bodies but of epistemes

- aiming for / guarantee a diversity of materials and technologies e.g. textile / embroidery
- Name it "Making"
- Makingspace instead of maker / makerspace (in German it is connotated with a male topic")
- establish a Protection concept
- care about children's rights
- aim for financial self-sufficiency.
- Fight inequality on an intersectional approach
- Working on topics close to the communities
- have a look on other communities: citizen making / neighbourhoods / open community
- Technology as a means to promote autonomy and strengthen communities' potential to create their own solutions
- Integrate Local Knowledge

WORST PRACTICES

One strong criticism is the reduction of Making Activities as a promising path for STEM education, without questioning the goals of the latter. Consequently, treating Making as a strategy for a different purpose while neglecting openness, sharing and participation clearly misses its inherent characteristics and was equally criticized. Finally, both the production of physical artefacts and the technology used for doing so contribute to social and environmental problems. The political aspects of Technology and Making should not be ignored within the educational context but deliberately addressed.

"Making" as a toy for STEM education

- equating STEM education with making
- rewarding most technical / complex solutions

- Use of ready to projects and products: the way of learning and experiencing will be narrowed / the chance of real transformative maker education would be wasted! (e.g. lego)
- Teaching emerging technology without content/ real use case (e.g. Tiny ML, LoRaWAN...)
- learn how to use tools instead of learning how to solve problems with different tools
- Technology just for the sake of technology
- A narrow understanding of what technology is

Neglecting openness, sharing and participation

- To use the term "Citizen participation" but not real engagement, collaboration, connection etc.
- Not making the discussion about open, free and closed. Even if you are choosing to not use it, it is necessary to do it consciously.
- To make / design something for the target group instead of with them
- Access is often limited - open doors even if places are in museums or schools would be great!
- Not valuing local knowledge and local technologies

Neglecting social and environmental responsibility

- Printing just for test
- tool driven ("every school needs a 3d printer")
- Working for Microsoft "in the name of good will"
- proprietary-only makerspaces
- not taking into account that we are in a climate emergency and pretend that we don't have it
- Not taking into account that we live in an unequal world and that inequality is intersectional and should be taken into account

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Though Making Activities altogether gain visibility and popularity, there is a lack of a framework that defines Making and Critical Making, clearly describes its objectives but also its distinctions. This equally bears risks and opportunities for a critical perspective on Making in Education. The concept gets loosely and widely copied and adapted, in its seemingly flexible and undemanding manner but thereby also risks of leaving its purpose and characteristics behind. Maker Education would benefit from a critical perspective on Making and including this perspective also in its educational purposes. The feedback of the invented Maker Education experts on Best and Worst Practices makes this particularly clear. Below we offer a first suggestion on how to integrate Critical Making with Education in general as a basis for further exploration on a framework for “Critical Maker Education”.

LOCAL AND CONNECTED

Fab Labs, Open Workshops and Makerspaces usually have strong ties to their location and community. Children and youth gain from concepts that are less abstract but address topics that are linked to their personal lives.

SOCIAL

Education prepares for creating one's own, but also a globally more equal future. Education should focus on developing responsible, ethical and social mindsets among young people.

REFLEXIVE

We currently live more than ever in an unsustainable, unequal world and directly feel the limits and consequences. Education needs to provide young people with the tools to be critical on one's own decisions but also on existing power structures.

IMPACTFUL

Young people need to understand the impact of their own voices and actions to transform the world and change direction. It is the purpose of education to show children that they are in fact having an impact and the power to invent and create. And that they are not limited to following existing rules and demands.

JOYFUL AND MEANINGFUL

Children and youth, in fact humans, are curious and naturally interested to learn and understand. Education should spark this joy and allow the learners to explore and invent and add meaning to their learning.

As mentioned previously, this has been a first step to approach the broad range and extensive number of activities linked to Making in education in Germany, which serves as a European case example. It gives us good insights into good and bad practices of Maker education. In a next step we want to explore if and how these initiatives are linked to the broader Maker Community and whether the educational programmes can be seen “critical” in the sense of critical making and RRI.

REFERENCES

- Blikstein, P., Martinez, S. L., & Allen Pang, H. (2016). Meaningful making: Projects and inspirations for fab labs + makerspaces.
- Dali, Birta (2015). The making of future entrepreneurs. The relationship between Fablabs and entrepreneurial intentions of students in upper secondary school, [https://docs.google.com/document/d/1a6j-Zmalzs0Vr5IEDkUf61cwHoM5TMV4tlqWU-5paI8/edit#Thesis at the Haskoli Islands#](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1a6j-Zmalzs0Vr5IEDkUf61cwHoM5TMV4tlqWU-5paI8/edit#Thesis%20at%20the%20Haskoli%20Islands#)
- Dougherty, D. (2012). The maker movement. *Innovations: Technology, governance, globalization*, 7(3), 11-14.
- Euler, M. & Weßnigk (2011). Schülerlabore und die Förderung kreativer Potentiale. *Plus Lucis*, 1-2/2011, https://www.pluslucis.org/ZeitschriftenArchiv/2011-1_PL.pdf [05.07.2021].
- MacDowell, P. (2021). Design Principles for Teaching Sustainability Within Makerspaces. *Teacher as Designer: Design Thinking for Educational Change*, 133-147.
- Schön, S., Voigt, C. & Jagrikova, R. (2018). Social innovations within makerspace settings for early entrepreneurial education - The DOIT project. In T. Bastiaens, J. Van Braak, M. Brown, L. Cantoni, M. Castro, R. Christensen, G. Davidson-Shivers, K. DePryck, M. Ebner, M. Fominykh, C. Fulford, S. Hatzipanagos, G. Knezek, K. Kreijns, G. Marks, E. Sointu, E. Korsgaard Sorensen, J. Viteli, J. Voogt, P. Weber, E. Weippl & O. Zawacki-Richter (Eds.), *Proceedings of EdMedia: World Conference on Educational Media and Technology* (pp. 1716-1725). Amsterdam, Netherlands: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). Retrieved June 22, 2021 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/184401/>.
- Schön, Sandra; Friebel, Luisa; Braun, Clarissa; Ebner, Martin; Eder, Julia: Makerspaces zur Wissenschaftsvermittlung und Innovationsraum der neuen Generation - In: Hafer, Jörg [Hrsg.]; Mauch, Martina [Hrsg.]; Schumann, Marlen [Hrsg.]: *Teilhabe in der digitalen Bildungswelt*.

- Münster; New York : Waxmann 2019, S. 187-197 - URN:
urn:nbn:de:0111-pedocs-180237
- Baier, A. (Hrsg.). (2016). *Die Welt reparieren: Open Source und Selbermachen als postkapitalistische Praxis* (1. Auflage). Transcript.
- Blikstein, P., & Krannich, D. (2013, Juni). *The makers' movement and FabLabs in education: Experiences, technologies, and research (PDF Download Available)*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262173151_The_makers%27_movement_and_FabLabs_in_education_experiences_technologies_and_research
- BMBF. (2020, November 13). *Karliczek: Mehr MINT-Bildungsangebote für Jugendliche - BMBF*. Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung - BMBF. <https://www.bmbf.de/de/karliczek-mehr-mint-bildungsangebote-fuer-jugendliche-13073.html>
- BuB. (2016, Dezember 21). *Der Makerspace: Ort für Kreativität und Wissenstransfer*. Forum Bibliothek und Information. <https://b-u-b.de/makerspace/>
- Digital Literacy Lab. (o. J.). *Digital Literacy Lab*. Abgerufen 22. Juni 2021, von <https://dl-lab.org/>
- Förschler, A. (2018). Das „Who is who?“ der deutschen Bildungs-Digitalisierungsagenda. Eine kritische Politiknetzwerk-Analyse. *Pädagogische Korrespondenz*, 58, 31–52.
- Forum Arbeitslehre*. (2016). 16(2). https://gatwu.de/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Forum_Arbeitslehre_16_2_Web.pdf
- Ingold, S., Maurer, B., & Trüby, D. (2019). *CHANCE MAKERSPACE Making trifft auf Schule* (Nummer July).
- Katterfeldt, E.-S., Dittert, N., & Schelhowe, H. (2015). Designing digital fabrication learning environments for Bildung: Implications from ten years of physical computing workshops. *International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction*, 5, 3–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcci.2015.08.001>

- Leithold, I. (2017). *Calliope mini für Schulen: Geschenk oder Lobbyismus*. heise online. <https://www.heise.de/newsticker/meldung/Calliope-mini-fuer-Schulen-Geschenk-oder-Lobbyismus-3867025.html>
- Martin, L. (2015). The Promise of the Maker Movement for Education. *Journal of Pre-College Engineering Education Research (J-PEER)*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.7771/2157-9288.1099>
- Pinto, L. E. (2016). *Critical making takes a holiday*. 10.
- Resnick, M., & Rosenbaum, E. (2013). Designing for tinkerability. In *Design, make, play: Growing the next generation of STEM innovators* (S. 163–181).
- Stilz, M., Ebner, M., & Schön, S. (2020). Maker Education—Grundlagen der werkstatorientierten digitalen Bildung in der Schule und Entwicklungen zur Professionalisierung der Lehrkräfte. *Beiträge zur Lehrerbildung und Bildungsforschung*, 6.
- Tanenbaum, J. G., Williams, A. M., Desjardins, A., & Tanenbaum, K. (2013). Democratizing technology: Pleasure, utility and expressiveness in DIY and maker practice. *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2603–2612. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2470654.2481360>
- Torres, C. A., & Noguera, P. (2008). *Social Justice Education for Teachers: Paulo Freire and the Possible Dream*. BRILL. <https://brill.com/view/title/37556>
- Tuhkala, A., Wagner, M.-L., Iversen, O. S., & Kärkkäinen, T. (2019). Technology Comprehension—Combining computing, design, and societal reflection as a national subject. *International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction*, 20, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcci.2019.03.004>
- Stilz, M.; Mennicke, J. „FabLabs und Offene Werkstätten als außerschulischer Lernort“ In: Lena Beyer, Claudia Gorr, Caroline Kather, Michael Komorek, Peter Röben, Simona Selle (Hrsg.): Orte und Prozesse außerschulischen Lernens erforschen und weiterentwickeln. Tagungsband zur 6. Tagung Außerschulische Lernorte an der Carl von

Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg. LIT Verlag Münster. 2021

Wittemyer, R., McAllister, B., Faulkner, S., McClard, A., & Gill, K. (2014).
Makehers: Engaging girls and women in technology through making,
creating, and inventing. Study by Intel Corporation.